

GT2 - Imagem, Edição e Tecnopoéticas

Mediums used and promoted in pedagogic art handbooks: three cases of the XX century

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RESUMO

Este trabalho, interessado em manuais para educação e produção artística, propõe revisar uma seleção de três textos, *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* (Neufert, 2013 edição em espanhol); *The fluxus performance workbook* (Friedman, edição de 2002); e *Hacia una educación sonora* (Murray, edição em espanhol de 2006), com o objetivo de identificar em cada um deles a presença de características multi, inter e/ou transmídia, para posteriormente compará-los entre si. Esses manuais foram selecionados por terem sido criados como pedagogias, seja de ergonomia arquitetônica, ações ou som, durante o século passado. Embora todos tenham origem em campos diferentes, este ensaio busca reconhecer os meios empregados e fomentados, bem como analisar a relação entre eles. Nossa intenção é apontar semelhanças e diferenças que nos permitam melhor compreendê-los a partir da perspectiva que foi definida.

Palavras-chave: manuais; pedagogia; intermedia; transmídia

ABSTRACT

*This work, interested in handbooks for education and artistic production, proposes to review a selection of three texts, *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* (Neufert, 2013 Spanish edition); *The fluxus performance workbook* (Friedman, 2002 edition); and *Hacia una educación sonora* (Murray, 2006 Spanish edition), with the objective of identifying in each one the presence of multi, inter and/or transmedia features, to later compare them with each other. These handbooks were selected for having been created as pedagogies, be it architectural ergonomics, actions, or sound, during the last century. Although all of them were originated in different fields, this essay seeks to recognize the mediums used and promoted, as well as to analyze the relationship between them. Our intention is to point out similarities and differences that allow us to better understand them from the perspective that was set.*

Keywords: handbooks; pedagogy; intermedia; transmedia

INTRODUCTION

The term medium can have different meanings according to the context where it is found. From an art perspective,

Medium can refer to both the type of art (e.g. painting, sculpture, printmaking), as well as the material an artwork is made from [...] For example, a sculpture in the medium of

bronze or marble; a painting in the medium of oil paint on canvas, or watercolor on paper; a drawing in the medium of pencil or crayon; a print in the medium of etching or lithography. (TATE, n.d.)

The word medium is frequently confused with the idea of media. José Luis Brea (2002) has pointed at the difference between those concepts. He explains that medium is “...*la materia sobre la que un contenido de significancia cobra cuerpo, se materializa.*”¹ and that media is “...*un dispositivo específico de distribución social del conocimiento...*”². A great example that he presents to illustrate this difference is a magazine. The paper on which it is printed is the medium, while the magazine itself, no matter if it is printed, electronic or spoken, is a media. He also states that multimedia is often used to refer to “... *aquella producción que incorpora elementos desarrollados en distintos soportes.*”³, although the right term to call this according to him should be “multi means”.

According to Mieko (2013), during the 1960s, Fluxus artists considered the word *media* as a synonym for *medium*, as a vehicle to express through art, such as language, sound or light. But that concept, says Mieko, has changed over time and other words have derived from it. Dick Higgins, one of Fluxus founder members, spread the term intermedia as “the form of expression which falls between the existing genres such as poetry and music, for example, vocal poem or visual poem”⁴.

The idea of intermedia was also present in the art major program developed by George Maciunas between 1968 and 1969, which had a four-year curriculum. During the first two years “Workshop blocks will present comprehensive training and experience in technologies of various media and their interrelationships [...] Inter-block collaboration, movement of staff, and students

¹ “...the matter on which a meaningful content gets a body, materializes.” [Own translation] BREA, José Luis. *La era postmedia. Acción comunicativa, prácticas (post)artísticas y dispositivos “neomediales”*. Salamanca: Consorcio Salamanca, 2002. P.6

² “...a specific device of social distribution of knowledge...” [Own translation] *Ídem*

³ “...that production which brings together elements that were developed in different means.” [Own translation] *Ídem*

⁴ MIEKO, Shiomi. *Intermedia/Transmedia*. Moma Website. Available in: <https://post.moma.org/intermedia-transmedia/>. Last Access: 27/05/2023

and projects will be encouraged.”⁵. He illustrated these ideas in a circular scheme, where he placed four groups of art fields, like in a roulette. Close to the bottom of that roulette, he wrote the word *intermedia* and he included a tab close to that term.

Transmedia also came from the word medium. According to Mieko (2013), transmedia was a method begun by Maciunas (although he didn’t use that word) that “...has to do with the creation of conceptually related works in different mediums. For example, if I start with an Event, I turn it into an object, a musical work, and then into a video. The original concept is carried into subsequent works even though the form of expression is different each time.”⁶ Mieko explains that transmedia is like the words transfer or transit. When a person travels, they change from one means of transportation to another to be able to continue their journey. The same happens in transmedia, an artwork evolves in different channels.

Before entering our exploration, it is important to point out that as handbooks, the texts that were chosen, share that they are pedagogic. This could seem obvious, but Boulboullé (2018) explains that only three hundred years handbooks got their educational nature, which they didn’t use to have originally. She claims that art wasn’t the main topic in the first handbooks. They used to be small books that could be kept at hand and their topic was mostly related to religion. In our time, handbooks have become a tool that teach us something, that allow us to relate theory and practice.

ARTE DE PROYECTAR EN ARQUITECTURA

Arte de proyectar en arquitectura, written by Ernst Neufert, was first published in 1936. It is an ergonomics reference text that should be seen as a handbook according to the prolegomena written by the author himself. It begins by: “*Este manual surgió a partir de la*

⁵ MACIUNAS, George. *Curriculum Plan*. George Maciunas / Fluxus Foundation Inc. Website. Available in <http://georgemaciunas.com/essays-2/improving-education-in-the-world-based-on-maciunas-knowledge-management-and-learning-machine-system-by-astrit-schmidt-burkhardt/>. Last Access: 27/05/2023

⁶ MIEKO *Loc. Cit.*

*documentación recogida para impartir una conferencias en la Bauhochschule de Weimar*⁷. Also, it should be considered as a pedagogic book since Meister (2018) has described it as a volume that “...has arguably educated more of Germany’s architects and shaped more its architectural heritage and current production than any architectural schools or famous masters”⁸.

This time we will focus on the *2013 Spanish edition*, one of the many that have been published in several languages (eighteen international editions in 2018). Is it possible for *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* to promote inter or transmedia even if it is made on a single medium (screen or paper)? This handbook is addressed to architects, whose work, consciously or not, is strongly related to both, transmedia (while projecting) and multimedia (while building). Each time an architectural project is made, it is a common practice for architects to communicate their ideas using different languages (verbal or visual), various views (in plan, elevation, isometrics), and diverse mediums (drawings on paper, models on wood or gypsum). Focusing on the mediums, one single idea is transferred to drawings, models and pictures, repeating it over and over again on different channels to make sure that it is clear for the client, the builder, the workers, or anyone who is looking at it. The principles of ergonomics set in *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* are used to project architecture, which is presented in several vehicles. It could be claimed that *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* may promote transmedia because it sets the laws of ergonomics that are considered while projecting. Once the construction is over, the building itself along with the plans, models and drawings have a transmedia nature. Certainly, this depends on each project because some of them could be carried out using only one medium.

On the other side,

Construction co-ordination drawings...are drawings that together convey the architect’s instructions for how a building should be assembled [...] When the construction drawings are issued, the layers of the drawing have to be separated so that they can be

⁷ “This handbook arose from the collected documentation to give some lectures at the Weimar Bauhochschule.” [Own translation] NEUFERT, Ernst. *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura*. Mexico City. Gustavo Gili: 2013. P.VI

⁸ MEISTER, Anna-Maria, Formatting Modern Man on Paper : Ernst Neufert’s « Lehren ». History of Knowledge website. Available in <https://historyofknowledge.net/2018/05/21/formatting-modern-man-on-paper/#fn-1>. Last access : 27/05/2023

read by the different subcontractors, but the architects have to make their decisions across the layers. (DRAWING MATTER, n.d.)

While building, several elements in different mediums are put together to create a whole structure, including bricks, pipes, cables, and other. *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* may promote multimedia because it appoints the laws of ergonomics that are applied while all this components are arranged in one work. Of course, this depends on the particular work because some of them could be built using only one medium.

Depending on each case, it could be claimed that, while projecting, intermedia is not typically fostered by *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* because each drawing, model or picture that is made during the project isn't located between two genres, but it clearly belongs to only one. Not often a project is shown from, for example, in a drawing-model. Also, it would be possible to assert that, while building, intermedia is not typically promoted by *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* because each expert usually brings a part of the work that is well differentiated, such as masonry or carpentry.

HACIA UNA EDUCACIÓN SONORA

Hacia una educación sonora, written by the Canadian musician Murray Schafer, was published in 1992 by Arcana Editions. In the 2006 Spanish edition Lidia Camacho, who wrote the foreword, admits that the original book's title (*A Sound Education*) has two meanings, "an education of sound" and "a good education". This is the best prove that we can find in this book of its intention to be pedagogical.

An essential concept for this book is soundscape, which is the "... *campo sonoro total, cualquiera que sea el lugar donde nos entremos. Es una palabra derivada de landscape (paisaje); sin embargo, y a diferencia de aquella, no está estrictamente limited a also lugares*

*exteriores.*⁹⁹. The author thinks that to improve our soundscape we must learn to listen and after we would be able to create socially committed projects that allow us to design our sound surroundings. According to him, the easiest way to help people learn how to listen was creating a series of exercises. Murray developed one hundred exercises and put them together in what could be considered as a handbook since he called his collection *Ear cleaning exercises*. He divided it in three sections showing no physical boundaries, placing those exercises related to perception and imagination at the beginning of the book, those related to sound production in the middle, and those related to society at the end.

Of course, the used medium was only one (each exercise is printed on paper), but the promoted mediums were different. We have taken a couple exercises from the second section of the book in order to establish their proximity to the promotion of multi, inter or transmedia. Exercise number 20 is the first one that we considered to belong to the section devoted to sound production. It instructs the reader to imagine that the facilitator is holding a shovel and to produce sounds with his/her voice while the facilitator digs on different materials such as sand or coal. This exercise promotes the creation on only one medium (air). It's not possible to assert that multi, inter or transmedia are being fostered because all of them need the presence of at least two mediums.

The second exercise (number 67) has also been considered by us as a part of the sound production section. It asks the reader to pick up a sound that seems to be disappearing from his/her soundscape and to record it. The exercise also tells the reader to catalogue the recording by adding information such as the date, the history of the recorded object or the current location. It is important to mention that the instructions don't specify if the information should be recorded or written, so this activity, depending on how it is done, could promote production on a single medium or on several that repeat the same idea on different channels (transmedia). Also, the instructions don't point at the medium that should be used to record, so the recording could

⁹ "...total sound field, wherever we are. It is a word derived from landscape; however, and unlike that one, is not strictly limited to outdoor places" [Own translation] SCHAFER R., MURRAY. *Hacia una educación sonora*. Mexico City. Consejo Nacional para la Cultura y las Artes: 2006. P. 12

be made on a cassette, a cd, hdd, or any other. It can't be claimed that multimedia is being fostered because all the elements would need to show different ideas on unlike mediums. Also, it can't be stated that intermedia is being encouraged since sounds and words contribute with a part of the work that is well differentiated.

THE FLUXUS PERFORMANCE BOOK

The third handbook that we chose to examine from the perspective of the mediums that are used and proposed is *The Fluxus Performance Workbook*. It was edited by Ken Friedman, Owen Smith and Lauren Sawchyn and published in 2002 by Performance Research Publications. It is free and available electronically only. The introduction makes a short tour through the history of Fluxus¹⁰ Event scores¹¹ which are, according to Friedman and Smith, "...proposals, propositions, and instructions"¹². This means that the authors recognize the book to be a handbook, besides the use of the term *workbook* in the title.

The introduction also points at important moments such as the 1980s, when the largest collection of scores, compiled by Jon Hendrick, was easily available only for researchers, but not for artists who wanted to learn from them. This motivated Friedman to publish *The Fluxus Performance Workbook* and helps us notice the pedagogic nature of that handbook.

The book is divided in forty-three sections, each of which corresponds to an artist. We chose a couple of scores made by Lithuanian artist George Maciunas (1931-1978), founder of

¹⁰ "Fluxus is an international avant-garde collective or network of artists and composers founded in the 1960s and still continuing today" TATE. Available in : <http://www.tate.org.uk/art/art-terms/f/fluxus> Last access: 20/05/2023

"Fluxus artists sought a closer integration of art and life and a more democratic approach to creating, receiving and collecting art." DEMPSEY, Amy. *Styles, schools and movements*. London: Thames and Hudson, 2010. 228-229

¹¹ "Events tend to be scored in brief verbal notations. These notes are known as event scores. In general sense they are proposals, propositions, and instructions." FRIEDMAN, Ken; SMITH, Owen; SAWCHYN, Lauren. *The Fluxus Performance Workbook*. London: Performance Research Publications, 2002. P. 1

"George Brecht, uno de los artistas más importantes asociados a Fluxus...presentó acciones que básicamente consistían en instrucciones escritas, como si fueran partituras musicales, que alguien (un actor) debía representar, como en *Three Aqueous Events* (1961)..." "...George Brecht, one of the most important artists associated to Fluxus...presented actions that basically consist of written instructions, as if they were musical scores, that someone (an actor) had to represent as in *Three Aqueous Events* (1961)..." [Own translation] AZNAR, Sagrario. *El arte de acción*. Donostia/San Sebastián: Nerea, 2016. p. 31

¹² FRIEDMAN *Loc. Cit.*

Fluxus. The first score that we chose is *Duet for Full Bottle and Wine Glass* (date unknown). Friedman, Smith and Sawchyn included a note before the score to explain that even if what they printed is a list, the piece is performed using a chart. The words of the list are put in the left column and numbers are written in the first row to indicate the duration of each action. The chart is filled and then each action is carried out to make sound. The list includes sixteen actions that are ordered somehow, following the steps of a strange wine tasting. Some of them are mentioned in chart (Chart 1).

Chart 1. Chart based on *Duet for Full Bottle and Wine Glass* by George Maciunas.(Own elaboration)

	1 to 2 seconds	2 to 3 seconds	3 to 4 seconds	4 to 5 seconds
Shaking				X
Opening corked bottle	X			
Gargle			X	
Spitting	X			

Duet for Full Bottle and Wine Glass encourages transmedia because one single idea is presented on two different vehicles, paper or screen (list and chart) and the body¹³ (actions). Multimedia is not promoted because although the score and the actions use different mediums, the concept is the same. Intermedia is not promoted either since writing and actions, don't share any territory in this piece.

The second score is *In Memoriam to Adriano Olivetti* (1962). The executors are instructed to use as a score an old calculator machine tape. Each number should be understood as a metronome beat and each performer should be assigned a number. When a number that belongs

¹³ According to the Ireland's National Cultural institution for Modern and Contemporary Art (IMMA) "A defining characteristic of Performance Art is the body, considered the primary [Medium](#) and conceptual material on which Performance Art is based. Other key components are time, space and the relationship between performer and audience." IMMA. Available in: <https://imma.ie/what-is-art/series-1-1970-now/performance-art/>. Last access: 27/05/2023.

We recognize other positions such as Peggy Phelan's idea of "Performance's only life is in the present" (Phelan, 2005, p. 146) through which she doesn't admit any sketches made before actions or any documentation made after; and Westerman and Wood (2020) who say that the importance given to the medium of performance art began in the 1960s and continued with Phelan. He leaves behind ideas like "performance art is a medium" or "the meaning of performance art is in itself, so it doesn't matter if it is present or not" and proposes to focus in its relation with the audience through two ideas: the calling of spectators and how those spectators get in touch with art history.

to an executor shows he/she has to perform the beat making actions such as raising his/her hat or making sounds such as tongue clicks. Performers are able to do all the same or different action, and they're also allowed to do the same or different sound. It is also mentioned that performers should rehearse to create defined actions or sounds and to follow the rhythm.

It is interesting about this work that the score written in text refers to another score written in numbers on a calculator's tape and to the actions that should be made. This arises questions like is it about two scores? Is one inside of the other? Is it about a single score and its attachment? It is only possible to assert that the score(s) and the action are the same idea in different mediums, so this piece promotes transmedia. It couldn't be asserted that multimedia is fostered because although the elements that integrate the work are on different channels, they share the same concept. Intermedia is not encouraged neither because there is not a middle ground between writing and actions in this piece.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Arte de proyectar en arquitectura may promote production on one or more mediums at the two different stages of architecture that we have highlighted, the project and the execution. While the architectural project is being carried out *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* may foster the production of one single medium or transmedia; and when the building is being put up *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* may stimulate the production of one single medium or multimedia. The mediums used in the project and the building don't necessarily match. Each case is different. For instance, a very developed project can be partly built, which means that transmedia can be greatly fostered, while multimedia is not promoted at all, and viceversa. And of course, neither transmedia nor multimedia could be stimulated if the project is shown in only one way and if the work is built with the work of a single expert. Further studies could analyze particular projects and works of architecture to explore the way *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* fosters transmedia and/or multimedia.

In *Hacia una educación sonora*, every exercise is different regardless of the section to which they belong. In the two cases that we examined, they stimulate production on a single medium and transmedia respectively, which allows us to assert that the whole book promotes production on one or more mediums and that transmedia is fostered. A deep study of each of the exercises is needed to determine which medium promotion prevails in each part of the book, and in the whole book.

In *The Fluxus Performance Workbook* too, every exercise is different. In the case examined, two of the eight Maciuna's exercises that were included, the artist promotes transmedia because the scores that he made and the actions derived from them are the same, while they're on two or more different channels. This happens throughout the whole handbook as we see that the scores of the forty-three artists are presented. In this case, further study is necessary beyond the general transmedia nature of this handbook to know the mediums promoted by each exercise and to approach towards the understanding of the questions mentioned in section three.

The three books that we examined, share their nature as pedagogic handbooks, and also, the use of a single medium (paper or screen) and their ability to promote various relationships between mediums, although in a different way. *Arte de proyectar en arquitectura* may promote transmedia in architectural projects and multimedia in their execution. *Hacia una educación sonora* fosters single-media or transmedia depending on each exercise and on the reader's interpretation. And *The Fluxus Performance Workbook* encourages transmedia considering that instructions show the same idea as the actions to be developed. Although there's still much research to be done, hopefully this essay will help particularly architects, listeners and artists to create from the mediums awareness.

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